

**COLLISIONAL LINE WIDTHS OF AUTOPERTURBED N₂: MEASUREMENTS
AND QUANTUM CALCULATIONS**

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Franck THIBAULT^{a,*}, Raúl Z. MARTÍNEZ^b, Dionisio BERMEJO^b, Laura GÓMEZ^{b,c}

^aInstitut de Physique de Rennes, UMR CNRS 6251, Université de Rennes I, F-35042 Rennes,
France

^bInstituto de Estructura de la Materia, IEM-CSIC, Serrano 123, 28006 Madrid, Spain

^cArea de Investigación e Instrumentación Atmosférica ,Instituto Nacional de Técnica
Aeroespacial « Esteban Terradas », INTA, carretera de Ajalvir km 4, 28850 Torrejón de
Ardoz, Madrid, Spain

Mail:

Franck THIBAULT

Université de Rennes I, Campus de Beaulieu

Institut de Physique de Rennes, UMR CNRS 6251, Bât. 11B

F-35042 Rennes, France

* Corresponding author. Tel. 33223236182 ; fax 33223235662
E-mail address : Franck.Thibault@univ-rennes1.fr

Abstract

In this work we present new experimental and theoretical values for the line broadening coefficients of the Q-branch Raman lines of autoperturbed N₂. For the experimental determination of the coefficients, high resolution stimulated Raman spectra of the Q-branch of N₂ at different pressures were obtained at 77, 194 and 298 K. Simultaneously, quantum dynamical calculations, performed on two potential energy surfaces, were carried out for the system between 77 and 298 K, rendering a set of theoretical line broadening coefficients that could be directly compared to those obtained from present measurements and previous ones. Within the limit of considering the colliding molecules distinguishable we discuss the ortho and para contributions to the pressure broadening cross-sections. Because such calculations are time consuming we indicate routes to circumvent this difficulty. We observe a reasonable agreement between theoretical and experimental values of the collisional line broadening coefficients at all the studied temperatures.

Keywords : Collisional broadening, linewidths, pressure broadening, nitrogen.....

1. Introduction

Laser spectroscopy is a powerful tool for atmospheric monitoring and combustion diagnostics. However, in order to be able to obtain good interpretations of the experimental measurements and reliable theoretical models, an accurate knowledge of the values of the collisional parameters (broadening and shifting coefficients) of the molecules found in both media is needed. Nitrogen is one of the main components of atmospheric and combustion media and, as a consequence, a large number of studies presenting high temperature measurements of the collisional parameters of N_2 , from room temperature to several thousand kelvins, can be found in the bibliography [1-3]. However, very little data are available for the broadening coefficients of autoperturbed N_2 at low temperatures [4, 5]. Several applications would benefit from the availability of these data: CARS and spontaneous Raman experiments used for thermometry and fluid dynamics studies in low temperature environments are a prime example (they typically involve gas expansions and/or flow systems; see [6] for an early experiment). In the field of atmospheric studies, high resolution Raman LIDAR setups require the knowledge of the broadening coefficients of the spectral lines for the correct interpretation of the observations [7].

In this work we present new experimental values for the self-broadening coefficients of the Q-branch lines of N_2 measured at 77, 194 and 298 K. The spectra were obtained with the high resolution Stimulated Raman Loss spectrometer in Madrid. Quantum dynamical calculations were performed considering the N_2 molecules as rigid rotors and distinguishable. Most of the line parameters quantum calculations found in the bibliography involve molecules perturbed by atoms [8-11], with only a few studies [12-22] addressing such calculations for diatom-diatom systems because of their complexity. For the present study we have used two potential energy surfaces (PESs). Namely, the modified version, by D. Cappelletti et al. [23], of the original PES of van der Avoird et al. [24] and the more recent ab initio PES of Gómez et al. [25]. Mainly the close-coupling (CC) method was used but because such calculations are time consuming additional calculations at high energies were performed with the less sophisticated coupled-states (CS) method. We will compare both methods at intermediate kinetic energies. In addition we will discuss the accuracy of theoretical results obtained without performing the thermal average but only performing the calculations at the kinetic energy associated to the mean relative speed at the temperature considered. The contribution of the two species (ortho and para) present in natural nitrogen to the measured broadening coefficient is also of interest; in order to be able to compare the result of the calculations with

the experimental measurements, the broadening coefficients have been calculated as a weighted sum of the contributions of the ortho and para species.

2. Experiments

2.1 Experimental details

The experimental setup used for our measurements has already been described in a previous paper [17], so only some details will be given here. We have recorded the Q -branch lines of the fundamental Raman band of pure nitrogen, from $j=0$ to $j=12$ at 77 K, from $j=0$ to $j=16$ at 194 K, and up to $j=18$ at 298 K. Transitions departing from higher rotational levels have not been recorded because, at these temperatures, these levels do not have enough population to produce a strong enough signal in our spectra. As in previous works, 0.4 cm^{-1} are approximately recorded in 18 minutes, averaging 10 laser shots and sampling the spectrum every second. We have tested that under these scan conditions distortion of the line profile is negligible. We have measured the spectra at several pressures for each considered temperature and for each studied line. The interval of pressures used was 5 to 50 mbar at 77 K, 10 to 100 mbar at 194 K, and 20 to 120 mbar at 298 K. Under these conditions line-mixing effects have not been observed in our spectra.

Each line of the spectra has been fitted to a Voigt profile using the Peak Fitting Module from Microcal Origin Software. The Gaussian width in these fits has been set to $3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 77 K, $5.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 194 K and $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 298 K. This value of the Gaussian width is obtained as the convolution of the Doppler width, γ_D , and the nearly Gaussian apparatus function, γ_{app} . In our experiment $\gamma_{\text{app}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and γ_D can be easily calculated for each temperature. As a result of the fit we obtain the Lorentzian width for every line and pressure, which is the width due to the collisional effects. To obtain the collisional line broadening coefficients, these Lorentzian widths are plotted versus pressure for each line and temperature. The points are fitted to a straight line whose slope yields the broadening coefficient for each spectral line.

2.2 Experimental results

The results of our measurements of the Q -branch line broadening coefficients for pure N_2 at 77 and 194 K are presented in Table 1. This table includes an additional set of measurements that were also performed in our laboratory, corresponding to the values of the line broadening coefficients of pure N_2 at 298 K. Since similar measurements at room

temperature had already been carried out years before [1], this last set of data does not provide new information. However, the good agreement between our measurements and those of Ref. [1], with deviations that are within the intervals defined by the error bars, represents an additional consistency check of our experimental procedure (see Table 1). Moreover, it allows the determination of the temperature dependence of the pressure broadening coefficients.

A typical scaling law used to describe the temperature dependence of the broadening coefficients for a given j quantum number is:

$$\gamma(T) = \gamma_0(T_0) \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right)^{n_j}, \quad (1)$$

where T_0 and γ_0 are a reference temperature and the corresponding broadening coefficient at that temperature respectively. Using the values of our experimental line broadening coefficients and $T_0=298$ K as reference temperature, it can be found that the exponent n_j varies between 0.587 for $Q(0)$ and 0.845 for $Q(10)$. The values of n_j are presented in Table 2 for values of j up to $j=12$.

3. Calculations

Dynamical calculations were performed on two different PESs. The first one is an ab initio PES [25,26] that from now on we will refer to as SAPT PES. The second one is a scaled PES [23] hereafter known as PES8. To obtain this latter surface, the N₂-N₂ Potential Energy Surface of van der Avoird et al. [24], denoted AWJ PES, was rescaled [23] by adjusting a few parameters on some transport coefficients. The most recent version of PES8 has been used for the determination of two-body rotational state-to-state rates [27], which are closely related to the parameters that interest us in the present study (see below).

Figure 1 compares these two PESs. In order to reduce CPU time, the analytical form of these surfaces is projected over 30 bispherical harmonics [17,18,24,28,29]. Technical details can be found in Ref. [17]. For future use Figure 2 also allows a comparison between the two PESs by showing their radial coefficients (see for instance Eq. (1) of Ref. 18).

Theoretical values of the collisional broadening parameters for auto-perturbed nitrogen Q -branch lines, at different temperatures, have been obtained from the MOLSCAT quantum dynamical code [30]. The collisional broadening cross-sections, using the impact approximation, can be expressed as a function of diffusion S -matrix elements [10,12-16]. The

coupled equations were solved using the hybrid log derivative-Airy propagator of Alexander and Manolopoulos [31], with starting, mid and ending propagation distances at $R_{\min}=2.5 \text{ \AA}$, $R_{\text{mid}}=15 \text{ \AA}$ and $R_{\max}=25 \text{ \AA}$. Total angular momentum convergence is reached for values of J between 50 and 140 depending on the considered energy. Here, the total angular momentum, \vec{J} , is considered as the addition of the composed angular momentum of the colliding molecules, \vec{j}_{AB} , and the momentum related to the relative motion of the colliding pair, $\vec{\ell}$.

At a given total energy our basis set includes all the energetically open rotational levels (j_A, j_B), where j_A and j_B stand respectively for the rotational quantum numbers of the optically active molecule and the perturber molecule, and corresponding to the total internal rotational energy given by $E(j_A, j_B) = B j_A(j_A+1) + B j_B(j_B+1)$ with $B = 1.989 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, plus asymptotically closed (j_A, j_B) levels which lie approximately 100 cm^{-1} above the total energy.[†] The figure of 100 cm^{-1} corresponds to about the maximum well depth of the $\text{N}_2\text{-N}_2$ PES. Thus, this is a shared energy among the monomers.

The experimental set-up studies natural N_2 ($n\text{N}_2$), a 2:1 mixture of ortho nitrogen ($o\text{N}_2, j$ even) and para nitrogen ($p\text{N}_2, j$ odd) and the intermolecular PES does not allow interconversion between ortho and para species [13,14,17,18]; therefore the broadening coefficient $\gamma(j_A, T)$ (in $\text{cm}^{-1}\text{atm}^{-1}$) at a given temperature T can be expressed as weighted sums of partial pressure broadening coefficients:

$$\gamma(j_A, T) = \frac{2}{3} \sum_{j_B \text{ even}} \rho_{j_B} \gamma(j_A, j_B, T) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{j_B \text{ odd}} \rho_{j_B} \gamma(j_A, j_B, T) \quad (2)$$

in which ρ_{j_B} is the normalized rotational population and

$$\gamma(j_A, j_B, T) = f \langle v \sigma(j_A, j_B, E_{\text{kin}}) \rangle \equiv f \bar{v} \sigma(j_A, j_B, T) \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma(j_A, j_B, T)$ is the Boltzmann average [18,27] over kinetic energy of the partial pressure broadening cross-sections $\sigma(j_A, j_B, E_{\text{kin}})$. f [32] converts[‡] the units of the dynamical rate constants ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) to those of the spectral linewidths ($\text{cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$) :

$$f = \frac{D}{2\pi c} \frac{273}{T}, \text{ where } D \text{ is the density number at STP } (D = 2.69109 \text{ molecule cm}^{-3}) \text{ and } c \text{ is}$$

[†] For instance for a run consisting of a $o\text{N}_2$ molecule colliding with a $p\text{N}_2$ molecule the basis set at a total (kinetic + rotational) energy of 261 cm^{-1} the basis includes 36 (j_A, j_B) states from (0,1) up to (0,13). Among them 9 levels are asymptotically closed.

[‡] note that Ref. 32 has a misprint; it indicates a conversion to $10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$.

the speed of light (in cm s^{-1}). \bar{v} is the mean relative speed associated to the thermal speed distribution: $\bar{v} = \sqrt{8k_B T / \pi \mu}$, where μ is the reduced mass of the colliding pair in u units.

In the rigid rotor approximation (where the PES is identical for the vibrational states $v=0$ and $v=1$), the dephasing term is missing and, in the specific case of isotropic Raman lines, $\sigma(j_A, j_B, E_{kin})$ can be expressed[§] as the sum of two-body rotational state-to-state cross-sections [13,14]:

$$\sigma(j_A, j_B; E_{kin}) = \sum_{j'_A \neq j_A, j'_B} \sigma(j_A j_B \rightarrow j'_A j'_B; E_{kin}) \quad (4)$$

Due to the triple bond of the nitrogen molecule any vibrational effect should be very small and previous studies confirm this approximation [33-35].

These ordinary state-to-state cross-sections (figuring in the 2nd member of Eq. (4)) were calculated using the close-coupling method over a grid of about 240 total energies varying from about 0 to 400 cm^{-1} and completed by 4 coupled-states calculations between 400 and 800 cm^{-1} . The CS method is expected to provide [14,36] a quite good approximation at high kinetic energy without the high computational cost a CC calculation would have required (the number of energetically accessible channels dramatically increases with energy). Mathematical extrapolations [22] were performed up to 2000 cm^{-1} in order to perform the thermal average. Fortunately, the calculations can also be speeded up by treating the oN₂-oN₂, oN₂-pN₂ and pN₂-pN₂ cases separately and by using a parallel version of the MOLSCAT code [37].

In our scattering calculations we considered the two colliding molecules as distinguishable, even for oN₂-oN₂ or pN₂-pN₂ collisions, thus neglecting the resonance -

[§] For subsequent users it should be noticed that the calculations of pressure broadening within the MOLSCAT code with ITYPE=3 (diatomic – diatomic) are incorrect. This is due to the fact that the subroutine “PRBR3” specially devoted to this case only handles the case where the perturbers rotational quantum numbers are identical ($j_2=j'_2$ in Eq. 7 of Ref.12). This has the effect of taking into account the elastic contribution, for the optically active molecule, $j_A=j'_A$ in Eq.4. This can be easily checked by summing individual cross sections (Eq.4) and comparing it with the pressure broadening cross section of an isotropic Raman Q(j_A) line directly provided by MOLSCAT (through the use of the built in PRBR and PRBR3 subroutines). This omission has little influence for systems like CO-H₂ or N₂-H₂ but may lead to significant errors for colliding molecules with comparable rotational constants. As already reported by Mengel et al [15] there is also an extra $(2j_2+1)$ factor.

exchange effects [38,39] (the so-called resonance broadening mechanism is reviewed in Ref. 11 p 239) and following what was done in [13,14]. **The plausible role of the identical molecule exchange symmetry on the line broadening is debated in Ref. 14 where it was ignored.** Recall that even rotational states combine only with symmetric nuclear spin function ($I_{N_2} = 0,2$) and odd rotational states combine only with anti-symmetric spin functions ($I_{N_2} = 1$). Only, the same species with the same nuclear spin are actually indistinguishable [14,27,36]. For an ortho- N_2 molecule colliding with nN_2 molecules 48.1% of the collisions are really **of indistinguishable type due to the statistical weights of the nuclear spins of nitrogen** while for a para- N_2 molecule only 33% of the collisions really involved indistinguishable molecule.

4. Discussions

Detailed calculations (paragraph 4.1 to 4.3) are reported for the use of the SAPT PES only.

4.1 Comparison between ortho and para pressure broadening cross-sections

Figures 3a – 3d show partial PB cross-sections as given in Eq. (4) for various $Q(j_A)$ lines and for some j_B values. The overall behaviour of such quantities is quite similar to the one plotted in Fig. 3 of Ref. 18 for the case of the $C_2H_2-H_2$ system and plotted in Fig. 1 of Ref. 22 for the N_2-H_2 system. However, in the present case we note that all these cross-sections are very close for kinetic energies greater than about 200 cm^{-1} , while this is the case at higher energies for the above mentioned systems [18,22], because of the smallness of the rotational constant (2 as compared to 60 cm^{-1}).

The corresponding thermally averaged partial PB cross-sections are reported Fig. 4a-4d. We observe a strong j_B dependence, especially for the very first j_A values, at the lowest temperature (77 K). However as the temperature increases there is little dependence of these quantities with j_B . We remind the reader that the most populated rotational nitrogen level is respectively 3, 4, 5 and 7 at 77, 113, 194 and 298 K.

Following Eqs. (2) and (4), in order to discuss the ortho and para contributions to a PB cross-section we can define a para and an ortho partial PB cross-sections (in \AA^2) for N_2 as:

$$\sigma_{pN_2}(j_A; T) = \sum_{j_B \text{ odd}} \rho_{j_B}(T) \sigma(j_A, j_B; T) \quad (5a)$$

$$\sigma_{oN_2}(j_A;T) = \sum_{j_B \text{ even}} \rho_{j_B}(T) \sigma(j_A, j_B; T) \quad (5b)$$

and thus a total PB cross-section:

$$\sigma(j_A;T) = \frac{2}{3} \sigma_{oN_2}(j_A;T) + \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{pN_2}(j_A;T) \quad (6)$$

The collision – induced pressure broadening cross-sections as defined in Eqs. (5) due to ortho and para species and the total PB cross-sections (Eq. (6)) are compared in Fig. 5a-5b for $T = 77$ K and 298 K. **Within our distinguishable molecules scheme, we** observe that the ortho and para contributions are in fact very close even at the lowest temperature. Such findings are important [18,21,22] with the objective of saving CPU.

4.2 Accuracy of the Coupled States Approximation

With the aim of saving CPU time we have performed a few calculations with the Coupled-states approximation (see Refs. therein 16 and 29). Our thermally averaged PB coefficients are CC-CS values rather than CC values because calculations were performed with both methods. Nonetheless, due to the fact that CS calculations were carried out for energies greater than 400 cm^{-1} , at the lowest temperature investigated and at least for the lowest j values, the results of our calculations may be qualified of CC results. As the temperature increases higher kinetic energies are involved in the MB thermal average and thus our results are more affected by the use of the CSA. However, the detailed study of state-to-state cross-sections performed by Huo and Green [36] for the present system shows that the use of the CSA is expected to be more accurate as the kinetic energy increases. Their calculations (see their Table 1) at 119 and 219 cm^{-1} show that the sum of CS inelastic cross-sections underestimate the CC sum of inelastic cross-sections. Figures 3a-3d confirm these observations. From these figures we expect that PB coefficients calculated with the CSA would be correct for temperatures greater than about 500 K.

4.3 Comparison between thermally averaged and not averaged pressure broadening cross-sections

We now discuss the accuracy of providing pressure broadening coefficients without performing the thermal average over the distribution in kinetic energies. This choice can be motivated by the prohibitive cost of the CC calculations and may be of some interest for subsequent users whatever the method used.

Within this approximation we consider that cross-sections are independent of energy and approximate the partial pressure broadening coefficient $\gamma(j_A, j_B, T)$ by its value at the mean relative speed \bar{v} , leading to:

$$\gamma(j_A, j_B, T) = f \bar{v} \sigma(j_A, j_B; \bar{E}_{kin}) \quad (7)$$

with \bar{E}_{kin} the kinetic energy associated with \bar{v} . Then Eq.2 can be rewritten as:

$$\gamma(j_A, T) = f \bar{v} \left[\frac{2}{3} \sum_{j_B \text{ even}} \rho_{j_B} \sigma(j_A, j_B, \bar{E}_{kin}) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{j_B \text{ odd}} \rho_{j_B} \sigma(j_A, j_B, \bar{E}_{kin}) \right] \quad (8)$$

Despite the differences observed in Fig. 3 at low kinetic energy there is good agreement even at 77 K ($\bar{E}_{kin} = 68.14 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) between the correct PB cross section values and the approximate ones as can be seen on Fig.5a. The largest differences are observed for $j_A=0$ and are about 5%. As expected (see Fig. 3) this agreement is better as j_A increases. Because the kinetic energy dependant cross-sections vary quite slowly and become smooth as the energy increases the agreement gets better as the temperature increases ($\bar{E}_{kin} = 263.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 298 K), see Fig. 5b. Again, due to the smaller rotational constant of N_2 as compared to the one of H_2 , this approximation is better justified at lower T than for C_2H_2 in H_2 [18,21] or N_2 in H_2 [22].

4.4 Comparison between the two PESs used

All the above comments based on the SAPT PES [25,26] are obviously still maintained with the use of the scaled PES [23]. However, as can be seen on Figs.1 and 2 these two PESs have non negligible differences and thus leading to different pressure broadening coefficients (Fig. 6). The ab initio PES is deeper by about 15%, for the maximum well depth, than the scaled PES. Both PESs show a similar overall anisotropy. However the SAPT PES is more anisotropic and the volume of its isotropic well is larger but their repulsive isotropic walls are very close.

The scaled PES leads to a good agreement with measured integral cross-sections and with second virial coefficients [23] which are mostly sensitive to the isotropic part of the PES. The quality of the SAPT PES, that is the first fully ab initio PES for this system, has also been tested for both kind of measurements. Although this PES leads to a good level of accuracy from this comparison it seems [26] that its isotropic volume is slightly too large. From their calculations of PB cross-sections of isotropic Raman linewidths at 113 K, Green and Huo [14] suggested that the anisotropy of the original PES of van der Avoird et al. [24] which is the starting material for the scaled PES [23] should be decreased. However, for data like PB

cross-sections which are mostly sensitive to the anisotropy the modified version of this PES leads only to slight changes [23]. Contrary to Huo and Green [14], Heck and Dickinson [40] suggested that the AWJ PES may be insufficiently anisotropic in regions sampled at low temperature. The ab initio PES clearly correct this apparent defect.

The SAPT PES leads to larger PB coefficients (Fig.6) than the scaled PES. This is due to a larger anisotropy, leading to more rotational exchanges, and a larger volume of its isotropic component, leading to more transfer between the linear and angular momenta. The average (over the j_A values) relative difference is about 6.5% at 77 K and about 3.5% at 298 K (relative to the results obtained with the SAPT PES). The influence of the larger well of the SAPT PES diminishing as the temperature increases.

4.5 Comparison between experimental results and calculated values

A comparison between the experimental and calculated line broadening coefficients is presented in Fig. 6. The calculated data at all four temperatures (77, 113, 194 and 298 K) have been computed specifically for this work using the CC and CS methods as described in earlier sections, while the experimental data sets have different origins: the ones at 77, 194 and 298 K obtained in the course of this work as described in the experimental section, the ones at 298 K measured by Rosasco et al [1], the ones at 295 K measured by Lavorel et al [2] and the ones at 113 K were measured by Herring et al. [5].

The availability of two prior experimental data sets obtained by other authors near the room T allows an initial comparison between them and the data set obtained for this work at 298 K. They are plotted in figure 6d, where it can be seen that the agreement is quite satisfactory. There is a small discrepancy between our data and those of Rosasco [1] and those of Lavorel [2], with our values being typically $\sim 5\%$ smaller for most rotational lines above $j=2$. The origin of this discrepancy might be in the different experimental conditions under which the measurements were carried out, which led to different models being used for the data fitting. Both prior works were conducted at higher pressures than ours, between approximately 50-2000 mb [1] and above 250 mb [2] respectively. Under these conditions line mixing becomes important and the authors had to introduce models to account for it in their data fitting procedures. The measurements carried out for this work, on the other hand, were conducted between 20 and 120 mbar, a range of pressures in which line mixing is almost negligible and a small contribution from Dicke narrowing can be expected only towards the upper limit of the range [1]. This allowed us to neglect both effects and fit our spectral data to Voigt line profiles. Thus, the differences in the final values of the broadening coefficients

might come from the different measurement conditions and line profiles employed in the three works. Nonetheless, and despite these small discrepancies, it is worth remarking that our results and those of other authors are generally in agreement with each other within the interval defined by the error bars associated with the measurements.

Regarding the comparison between experimental and calculated data, Figure 6 indicates that there is an overall good agreement between the experimental PB coefficients and the two set of calculations. The CC-CS results follow closely the temperature variation and the j dependence of the experimental ones. **Figure 7 exemplifies this temperature dependence and the good agreement observed between measurements and calculations for the Q(10) line.** In all cases the SAPT PES does a better job than the scaled PES.

At 77 K, the calculated results are close to the experimental ones except for the Q(1) line. As compared with the theoretical results the experimental data seem to fall off too quickly for $j > 8$. At 113 K the present calculated results are in better agreement with the experimental values of Herring and South [5] than were the calculated results of Green and Huo [14] using the AWJ PES [24]. They are also in good agreement with values determined from our experimental values in conjunction with Eq.1. At higher temperatures, 194 and 298 K, our CC-CS results are inside or very close the errors bars of the experimental data reported. The former appear to be slightly underestimated. This should be due to the use of the CSA at high energies.

5. Conclusion

We have provided new experimental pressure self-broadening coefficients for N_2 of interest for atmospheric applications and compared them to those obtained through quantum dynamical calculations. Detailed ortho-ortho and ortho-para partial pressure broadening cross sections provide similar contributions to the total pressure broadening coefficients allowing shortcuts to these time-consuming close coupling calculations. The CS approximation shows some defects but nevertheless should provide quite good results above room temperature. It is expected that the thermal average quadrature which requires the construction of a grid of cross sections at various energies is not necessary above the room T also allowing economy of CPU time. Quantum calculations performed on a scaled ab initio PES [23,24] provide only moderately good results. Better results are obtained using an ab initio PES [25,26]. Nonetheless, the history of N_2 - N_2 PESs is long [23-26,28] and certainly other PESs which have been tested on other kind of experimental data merit to be tested. Finally, the present

study will serve as a basis [40] on a very near future for testing and comparing more approximate methods like the semiclassical Robert-Bonamy method and the full classical method of Gordon which are useful for temperatures of interest in combustion processes.

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Table 1: Experimental values of the N₂-N₂ collisional line broadening parameter obtained at 77, 194 and 298 K, expressed in 10⁻³ cm⁻¹/atm as Half Width at Half Maximum (HWHM). Experimental errors are shown between parentheses.

<i>j</i>	<i>T</i> = 77 K	<i>T</i> = 194 K	<i>T</i> = 298 K	<i>T</i> = 298 K ^a
0	177.8 (10.3)	78.8 (6.6)	65.4 (11.2)	63.5 (15.0)
1	147.9 (5.3)	71.8 (10.0)	57.6 (4.6)	54.0 (6.0)
2	124.4 (6.9)	65.1 (4.2)	50.4 (3.0)	52.0 (2.0)
3	121.9 (7.1)	60.3 (5.1)	45.1 (4.8)	50.0 (3.0)
4	117.8 (7.8)	59.7 (4.7)	44.2 (4.6)	48.0 (2.0)
5	121.0 (7.1)	65.2 (10.6)	43.8 (3.2)	47.0 (2.0)
6	125.8 (6.6)	58.5 (4.8)	43.1 (2.9)	46.0 (2.0)
7	126.8 (10.1)	54.9 (3.9)	45.7 (3.0)	45.0 (4.0)
8	126.6 (9.0)	59.5 (4.9)	43.7 (3.6)	45.0 (2.0)
9	111.6 (4.8)	55.2 (4.0)	40.6 (3.4)	44.0 (4.0)
10	103.7 (4.9)	57.7 (3.5)	38.3 (5.6)	43.0 (3.0)
11	104.1 (11.3)	55.2 (5.6)	38.7 (6.6)	41.0 (5.0)
12	96.3 (8.0)	52.2 (5.6)	36.4 (4.2)	40.0 (2.0)
13	--	47.3 (3.3)	36.8 (2.9)	38.0 (3.0)
14	--	43.4 (3.1)	39.7 (3.8)	37.0 (3.0)
15	--	42.6 (4.1)	30.8 (5.1)	35.0 (5.0)
16	--	35.9 (5.0)	36.3 (4.5)	33.0 (4.0)
17	--	--	29.8 (3.5)	31.0 (8.0)
18	--	--	27.9 (2.9)	30.0 (6.0)

^a results of Ref. [1]

Table 2: Temperature dependence parameter, n_j , of Eq. (1) with $T_0=298$ K. Values of this parameter have been obtained from our experimental line broadening coefficients at 77, 194 and 298 K.

j	n_j
0	0.587
1	0.605
2	0.632
3	0.706
4	0.712
5	0.839
6	0.752
7	0.591
8	0.753
9	0.731
10	0.845
11	0.779
12	0.779

Figure captions

Fig.1: Comparison of the SAPT [25] (solid lines) and PES8 [23] (dashed lines) PESs for various geometries as indicated by their Jacobi angles (θ_1, θ_2, ϕ); for the definition of these geometries see a pictorial representations in Fig. 1 of ref. 28.

Fig. 2a: Comparison of the isotropic components of the PESs used (solid line SAPT [25], dashed line PES8 [23]).

Fig. 2b: Comparison of selected anisotropic components of the PESs used. For instance in the framed box 224 is set for the anisotropic component $V_{224}(R)$. They are normalized as in [24]. (solid line SAPT [25], dashed line PES8 [23]).

Fig. 3: variation with the kinetic energy of the partial pressure broadening cross-sections (Eq.4) for selected j_B values; (a) for $j_A=0$, (b) for $j_A=1$, (c) for $j_A=4$ and (d) for $j_A=5$.
CC and CS

Fig. 4 : Thermally averaged (at $T = 77, 113, 194$ and 298 K) partial pressure broadening cross-sections for selected j_B values; (a) for $j_A=0$, (b) for $j_A=1$, (c) for $j_A=4$ and (d) for $j_A=5$.

Fig. 5: Contributions of oN_2 and pN_2 (see Eqs 5) perturbers to the total cross-sections (Eq. 6); (a) $T = 77$ K, (b) $T = 298$ K.

Also, comparison between thermally averaged pressure broadening cross-sections and calculated values at the single kinetic energy associated with the mean relative speed at T .

Fig. 6: Comparisons between CC-CS pressure broadening coefficients obtained with the SAPT and PES8 PESs with present experimental values, experimental values of Herring and South [5], of avorel et al [2] and of Rosasco et al [1]. Values derived from the used of Eq.1 with Table 1 are also reported in (b). Estimated CC-CS values, calculated values on the AWJ PES [24], of Green and Huo [14] are reported at 113 and 298 K.
a) $T = 77$ K, (b) $T = 113$ K, (c) $T = 194$ K, (d) $T = 298$ K

Fig. 7: Log/log plot of the temperature dependence of the half-width at half maximum of the Q(10) line. Present experimental results and those of Ref. 5 are extrapolated (or interpolated) using Eq. 1 with $n = 0.845$ (table 1). Calculated values of Ref. 14 are estimated values from its Fig. 5.

Exp Lavorel à 295 K : si correction avec Eq.1 plus faibles de l'ordre de 1% donc sur la figure pas de corrections